

α – SUBGARMONIK FUNKSIYALAR**Obidjonov Islombek**

UrDU matematik injiniring kafedrası o’qituvchisi

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada $\mathbb{C}^n$ fazoda ikkinchi va uchinchi tartibli Kartan klassik sohalari yordamida aniqlangan matritsaviy halqalar uchun Loran yoyilmasining analogi olingan.

Аннотация. В этой работе получен аналог разложения Лорана для матричного кольца, определенного с помощью классической области Картана второго и третьего порядка в пространстве $\mathbb{C}^n$.

Annotation. In this work the analog of Laurent series is obtained for matrix ring, which is defined via the second and third type Cartan classical domain in $\mathbb{C}^n$.

Kalit so’zlar: golomorf funksiya, ikkinchi tip Kartan klassik sohasi, matritsaviy halqa, Loran qatori, Koshi, Hua Lo-Ken tipidagi integral.

Ключевые слова: голоморфная функция, классической области Картана второго порядка, матричного кольца, разложения Лорана, интеграл типа Хуа Ло-Кена.

Key word: holomorph function, classic domain of the second order Cartan, matrix ring, Lourent series, Hua Lo-Ken type integral.

 α – subgarmonik funksiyalar

Ma’lumki, garmonik va subgarmonik funksiyalar sinfi funksiyalar nazariyasida muhim o’rin tutib, matematik fizika, geometriya masalalarida ko’p qo’llaniladi. Klassik Dirixle masalasi biror $D \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ sohada $\Delta u = 0$, $u|_{\partial D} = \varphi$ tenglamaning yechimlari xususida bo’lib, bunday yechimning mavjudligi, yagonaligi, ularning xossalari garmonik analizning asosini tashkil qiladi. Ushbu maqola kompleks fazolarda garmonik va subgarmonik funksiyalar nazariyasini rivojlantiradigan α – garmonik va α – subgarmonik funksiyalar sinfini o’rganishga qaratilgan.

Ma’lumki, $\mathbb{C}^n$ fazoda Laplas operatori $dd^c u$ differensial forma bilan $dd^c u \wedge \beta^{n-1} = (n-1)! \Delta u dV$ kabi bog’lanishga ega bo’lib, bu yerda

$\beta = dd^c |z|^2$, $d = \partial + \bar{\partial}$, $d^c = \frac{\partial - \bar{\partial}}{4i}$. U holda $\mathbb{C}^n$ fazoda subgarmonik funksiya

umumlashgan ma’noda $dd^c u \wedge \beta^{n-1} \geq 0$ tengsizlik bilan ifodalanadi: ya’ni u yuqoridan yarim uzluksiz, $\overline{\lim}_{w \rightarrow z} u(w) \leq u(z)$ va $\forall \omega \geq 0$, $\omega \in F^{(0,0)}$ uchun

$dd^c u \wedge \beta^{n-1}(\omega) = \int u dd^c \omega \wedge \beta^{n-1} \geq 0$ tengsizlik bajarilsa, u funksiya $D \subset \mathbb{C}^n$ sohada

subgarmonik bo‘ladi, bu yerda $F^{(p,p)} = \{\omega \in \mathcal{F}^{(p,p)}(D) \cap C^\infty(D) : \sup p\omega \ll D\}$ - silliq va finit differensial formalar fazosi. Keyingi paytlarda standart Keli formasi $\beta = dd^c |z|^2$ o‘rniga ixtiyoriy musbat (1,1) bi-darajali α formani olish zaruriyati yuzaga keldi. Bunday holat, jumladan, m -sh funksiyalar sinfini o‘rganish (B. Abdullayev, S. Lu va boshqalar) p -plyurisubgarmonik funksiyalar va kalibrlangan geometriya masalalarida (Xarvi, Lauson), T-subgarmonik funksiyalarda ko‘zga tashlanadi.

Faraz qilaylik, $D \subset \mathbb{C}^n$ sohada C^2 sinfga tegishli, yopiq (1,1) bi-darajali differensial forma berilgan bo‘lsin.

Ta’rif 1. $D \subset \mathbb{C}^n$ sohada berilgan $u(z)$ funksiya

1) yuqoridan yarim uzluksiz bo‘lsa,

2) umumlashgan

ma’noda

$\int dd^c u \wedge \alpha^{n-1} \wedge \omega = \int u \wedge \alpha^{n-1} \wedge dd^c \omega \geq 0, \forall \omega \geq 0, \omega \in F^{(0,0)}$ bajarilsa, u ga α -subgarmonik funksiya deyiladi.

Bu ta’rifdan ko‘rinadiki, agar $\alpha = dd^c |z|^2$ bo‘lsa, biz subgarmonik funksiya ta’rifini olamiz.

Biz ushbu maqolada quyidagi xususiy hol uchun α -subgarmonik funksiyalar sinfini o‘rganamiz. $\alpha = (\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n) \in \mathbb{R}_+^n$ vektor uchun,

$$\varphi(z) = \alpha_1 z_1 \bar{z}_1 + \alpha_2 z_2 \bar{z}_2 + \dots + \alpha_n z_n \bar{z}_n$$

funksiyani olamiz va ushbu formani qaraymiz:

$$dd^c \varphi = \frac{i}{2} \partial \bar{\partial} \varphi = \frac{i}{2} \sum_{\substack{j=1, \\ k=1}}^n \frac{\partial^2 \varphi}{\partial z_j \partial \bar{z}_k} dz_j \wedge d\bar{z}_k =$$

$$= \frac{i}{2} (\alpha_1 dz_1 \wedge d\bar{z}_1 + \alpha_2 dz_2 \wedge d\bar{z}_2 + \dots + \alpha_n dz_n \wedge d\bar{z}_n).$$

$\alpha = dd^c \varphi$ deb olsak, u (1,1) bi-darajali musbat differensial formani beradi.

$D(D \subset \mathbb{C}^n)$ sohada berilgan $u \in C^2$ funksiya uchun quyidagi operatorni qaraymiz:

$$dd^c u \wedge \alpha^{n-1} = dd^c u \wedge (dd^c \varphi)^{n-1}. \quad (1)$$

$$dd^c \varphi^{n-1} = (n-1)! \sum_{j=1}^n \alpha_1 \alpha_2 \dots \overset{j}{\underset{\vee}{\alpha_n}} dz_1 \wedge d\bar{z}_1 \wedge \dots \wedge \overset{j}{\underset{\vee}{dz_n}} \wedge d\bar{z}_n$$

Bu yerda $\dots$ belgi shu ko‘paytmada j -had qatnashmasligini bildiradi.

$$(dd^c u) = \sum_{j,k=1}^n \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial z_j \partial \bar{z}_k} dz_j \wedge d\bar{z}_k \text{ tengliklardan}$$

$$dd^c u \wedge \alpha^{n-1} = (n-1)! \sum_j \alpha_1 \alpha_2 \dots \alpha_n \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial z_j \partial \bar{z}_j} dV$$

ifodaga ega bo‘lamiz.

Oxirgi tenglikdan ko‘rinadiki u funksiya uchun $dd^c u \wedge \alpha^{n-1} = 0$ tenglikni bajarilishi

$$\sum_j \alpha_1 \alpha_2 \dots \alpha_n \cdot \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial z_j \partial \bar{z}_j} = 0 \quad (2)$$

tenglikni bajarilishi bilan ekvivalent ekan.

Ta’rif 2. (2) tenglikni qanoatlantiruvchi $u \in C^2(D)$ funksiyaga α – garmonik funksiya deyiladi.

α – garmonik funksiyalar sinfi $\alpha - h(D)$ kabi belgilanadi. $\alpha = dd^c |z|^2$ bo‘lgan holda bu o‘zimizga ma’lum garmonik funksiyalar sinfiga ega bo‘lamiz. α – garmonik funksiyalarning ko‘pchilik xossalari garmonik funksiyalarning xossalari kabi bo‘lib, biz ularni keltirib o‘tirmaymiz.

Ushbu teorema α – garmonik funksiyalarning geometrik hususiyatini ifodalaydi:

Teorema 1. Agar $u(z)$ funksiya D sohada α – garmonik bo‘lsa, u holda $\forall z^0 \in D$ nuqta va

$$E(z^0, r) = \{ z \in \mathbb{C}^n : \alpha_1 |z_1 - z_1^0|^2 + \dots + \alpha_n |z_n - z_n^0|^2 = r^2 \} \subset\subset D \text{ ellipsoid}$$

uchun

$$u(z^0) = \frac{1}{\tilde{V}(r)} \int_{E(z^0, r)} u(\tau) dV(\tau)$$

tenglik o‘rinli bo‘ladi. Bu yerda $\tilde{V}(r)$ - ellipsoid bilan chegaralangan jism hajmi va $dV(\tau)$ – hajm elementi.

Isbot: Umumiylikni buzmaganda holda $z^0 = (0, 0, \dots, 0) \in D$ bo‘lsin deb olishimiz mumkin. Teoremaning isboti quyidagi sodda tasdiqdan kelib chiqadi: Agar $u \in \alpha - h(D)$ bo‘lsa, u holda

$$v(z_1, \dots, z_n) = u \left(\sqrt{\alpha_2 \dots \alpha_n} z_1, \dots, \sqrt{\alpha_1 \dots \alpha_n} z_j, \dots, \sqrt{\alpha_1 \dots \alpha_{n-1}} z_n \right)$$

funksiyaning D sohaning yuqoridagi chiziqli akslantirish natijasida hosil bo‘lgan obrazi D' da garmonik bo‘ladi.

Demak, v garmonik funksiya uchun o‘rta qiymat haqidagi teorema asosan ixtiyoriy $B(0, \rho) = \{z \in \mathbb{C}^n : |z_1|^2 + \dots + |z_n|^2 \leq \rho^2\} \subset\subset D'$ shart uchun

$$v(0) = \frac{1}{V(\rho)} \int_{B(0, \rho)} v(\xi) dV(\xi)$$

Ushbu integralda o‘zgaruvchini quyidagicha almashtiramiz:

$$\sqrt{\alpha_1 \dots \alpha_n} \xi_j = \tau_j \Rightarrow d\xi_j = (\sqrt{\alpha_1 \dots \alpha_n})^{-1} d\tau_j, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, n.$$

va $\alpha_1 |\tau_1|^2 + \dots + \alpha_n |\tau_n|^2 = \rho^2 \alpha_1 \dots \alpha_n$ tenglikda $r^2 = \rho^2 \alpha_1 \dots \alpha_n$ deb belgilab

olamiz va bundan $\rho = \frac{r}{\sqrt{\alpha_1 \dots \alpha_n}}$ kelib chiqadi. Ellipsoidning hajmi uchun

$$\tilde{V}(r) = \int_{E(0, r)} dV(\tau) = \int_{B(0, \rho)} (\alpha_1 \dots \alpha_n)^{n-1} dV(\xi) = (\alpha_1 \dots \alpha_n)^{n-1} V(\rho)$$

munosabat o‘rinli bo‘lishidan, quyidagi tenglik kelib chiqadi

$$\begin{aligned} u(0) &= \frac{1}{V(r)(\alpha_1 \dots \alpha_n)^{n-1}} \int_{\alpha_1 |\tau_1|^2 + \dots + \alpha_n |\tau_n|^2 \leq \rho^2} u(\tau_1, \dots, \tau_n) dV(\tau) = \\ &= \frac{1}{\tilde{V}(r)} \int_{\alpha_1 |\tau_1|^2 + \dots + \alpha_n |\tau_n|^2 \leq \rho^2} u(\tau_1, \dots, \tau_n) dV(\tau). \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Shunday qilib, (3) integral ellipsoid bilan chegaralangan soha bo‘yicha o‘rta qiymatni bildiradi. Teorema isbot bo‘ldi.

Shuningdek quyidagi teoremani o‘rinli ekanligini ko‘rish mumkin.

Teorema 2. Agar $u(z)$ funksiya D sohada α – garmonik bo‘lsa, u holda $\forall z^0 \in D$ nuqta va

$$E(z^0, r) = \{z \in \mathbb{C}^n : \alpha_1 |z_1 - z_1^0|^2 + \dots + \alpha_n |z_n - z_n^0|^2 \leq r^2\} \subset\subset D \text{ ellipsoid}$$

uchun

$$u(z^0) = \frac{1}{\sigma_n r^{2n-1}} \int_{\partial E(z^0, r)} u(\xi) d\sigma(\xi)$$

tenglik o‘rinli bo‘ladi. Bu yerda $d\sigma(\xi)$ - sirt elementi va σ_n – birlik ellipsoidning sirt yuzasi.

Endi α – subgarmonik funksiya ta’rifini beramiz.

Ta’rif 3. $D \subset \mathbb{C}^n$ soha berilgan bo‘lsin. Ushbu

$$\sum_{j=1, n} \alpha_1 \alpha_2 \dots \alpha_n \cdot \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial z_j \partial \bar{z}_j} \geq 0$$

tengsizlikni qanoatlantiruvchi $u \in C^2(D)$ funksiyaga α – subgarmonik funksiya deyiladi.

D sohada α – subgarmonik funksiyalar sinfini $\alpha - sh(D)$ kabi belgilaymiz.

Yendi α – subgarmonik funksiya xossalarini ko‘rib chiqamiz.

a) α – subgarmonik funksiyaning musbat koeffitsentli chiziqli kombinatsiyasi yana α -subgarmonik funksiya bo‘ladi ya’ni

$$u_k(z) \in \alpha - sh(D), b_k \in R_+ \Rightarrow b_1 u_1(z) + b_2 u_2(z) + \dots + b_m u_m(z) \in \alpha - sh(D)$$

$$k = \overline{1, m}$$

Bu yerda ham subgarmonik funksiyaning xossasi kabi xossa o‘rinli.

Teorema 3. Agar $u(z)$ funksiya D sohada α – subgarmonik bo‘lsa, u holda $\forall z^0 \in D$ nuqta va

$$E(z^0, r) = \{ z \in \mathbb{C}^n : \alpha_1 |z_1 - z_1^0|^2 + \dots + \alpha_n |z_n - z_n^0|^2 = r^2 \} \subset\subset D \text{ ellipsoid}$$

uchun

$$u(z^0) \leq \frac{1}{\tilde{V}(r)} \int_{E(z^0, r)} u(\tau) dV(\tau)$$

tenglik o‘rinli bo‘ladi. Bu yerda $\tilde{V}(r)$ - ellipsoid bilan chegaralangan jism hajmi va $dV(\tau)$ – hajm elementi.

Teorema 4. Agar $u(z)$ funksiya D sohada α – garmonik bo‘lsa, u holda $\forall z^0 \in D$ nuqta va

$$E(z^0, r) = \{ z \in \mathbb{C}^n : \alpha_1 |z_1 - z_1^0|^2 + \dots + \alpha_n |z_n - z_n^0|^2 \leq r^2 \} \subset\subset D \text{ ellipsoid}$$

uchun

$$u(z^0) = \frac{1}{\sigma_n r^{2n-1}} \int_{\partial E(z^0, r)} u(\xi) d\sigma(\xi)$$

tengsizlik o‘rinli bo‘ladi. Bu yerda $d\sigma(\xi)$ - sirt elementi va σ_n – birlik ellipsoidning sirt yuzasi.

Bu o‘rta qiymat haqidagi teoremlar yordamida α – subgarmonik funksiyalarning quyidagi xossalarini isboti kelib chiqadi.

b) Chekli sondagi α – subgarmonik funksiyaning maksimumi ham α – subgarmonik funksiya bo‘ladi ya’ni

$$u_1(z), u_2(z), \dots, u_m(z) \in \alpha - sh(D) \Rightarrow \max\{u_1(z), u_2(z), \dots, u_m(z)\} \in \alpha - sh(D).$$

c) Monoton kamayuvchi $\alpha -$ subgarmonik funksiyalar ketma-ketligining limiti $\alpha -$ subgarmonik funksiya bo‘ladi ya’ni

$$u_j(z) \in \alpha - sh(D), u_j(z) \geq u_{j+1}(z) \Rightarrow \lim_{j \rightarrow +\infty} u_j(z) \in \alpha - sh(D), j = 1, 2, \dots, n.$$

a) Tekis yaqinlashuvchi $\alpha -$ subgarmonik funksiyalar ketma-ketligi yana $\alpha -$ subgarmonik funksiyaqa yaqinlashadi ya’ni

$$u_j(z) \in \alpha - sh(D), u_j(z) \xrightarrow{-} u(z) \Rightarrow u(z) \in \alpha - sh(D), (k = 1, 2, 3, \dots)$$

ye) Maksimum prinsipi. Agar $u(z) \in \alpha - sh(D)$ funksiya biror $z^0 \in D$ nuqtada o‘zining maksimumiga erishsa, ya’ni

$$u(z^0) = \sup_{x \in D} u(x)$$

bo‘lsa, u holda $u(z) = const$ bo‘ladi.

f) $\alpha -$ subgarmonik funksiyalar umumiy holda C^2 sinfga tegishli bo‘lmasligidan, $\Delta_\alpha u -$ Laplas operatorini umumlashgan funksiyasi sifatida qarash mumkin, ya’ni

$$\Delta_\alpha u(\varphi) = \int u \cdot \Delta_\alpha \varphi, \quad \varphi \in F(D).$$

k) $\alpha -$ subgarmonik funksiyalar fazosida metrika quyidagi ko‘rinishga yega:

$$\rho(z, w) = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i |z_i - w_i|^2}$$

$D \subset \mathbb{C}^n$ sohada aniqlangan

$$u : D \rightarrow [-\infty, \infty)$$

funksiya berilgan bo‘lsin.

Ta’rif 4. Quyidagi ikkita shart o‘rinli bo‘lsa:

1) $u(z)$ yuqoridan yarim uzluksiz, ya’ni

$$\forall z^0 \in D \text{ uchun } \overline{\lim}_{z \rightarrow z^0} u(z) \leq u(z^0)$$

2) har bir $z^0 \in D$ nuqta uchun shunday $\rho(z^0) > 0$ topiladiki, $\rho \leq \rho(z^0)$ uchun

$$u(z^0) \leq \frac{1}{\tilde{V}(\rho)} \int_{\alpha_1 |z_1 - z_1^0|^2 + \dots + \alpha_n |z_n - z_n^0|^2 \leq \rho^2} u(\tau) dV(\tau)$$

shartni qanoatlantirsa, u holda $u(z)$ funksiya D sohada $\alpha -$ subgarmonik funksiya deyiladi.

$\alpha -$ subgarmonik funksiya va subgarmonik funksiyalarni farqli jihatlarini ko‘rsatuvchi misollarni ko‘rib o‘tamiz.

Misol: $\mathbb{C}^3$ fazoda bizga $\alpha = (2, 1, 2) \in \mathbb{R}_+^3$ vektor berilgan bo‘lsin.

$u = -|z_1|^2 + 1,5|z_2|^2 - |z_3|^2$ bu funksiya subgarmonik funksiya emas, lekin α – subgarmonik funksiya bo‘ladi.

Haqiqatan ham,

$$\Delta u = \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial z_1 \partial \bar{z}_1} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial z_2 \partial \bar{z}_2} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial z_3 \partial \bar{z}_3} = -1 + 1,5 - 1 = -0,5 \leq 0$$

bundan ko‘rinib turibdi u funksiya subgarmonik funksiya emas ekan, lekin quyidagiga asosan

$$\Delta_\alpha u = 2 \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial z_1 \partial \bar{z}_1} + 4 \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial z_2 \partial \bar{z}_2} + 2 \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial z_3 \partial \bar{z}_3} = -2 + 6 - 2 = 2 \geq 0$$

ya’ni u α – subgarmonik funksiya ekan.

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